

RESILIENT FEATURES OF A GRID-FORMING MULTI-PORT POWER CONVERTER

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ABSTRACT

Multiport power converters offer a conversion solution with improved efficiency and energy management. Grid-forming controllers can operate in weak and islanded grids. This paper introduces a grid-forming multiport power converter to support distribution network resilience, highlighting its key hard- and software features.

INTRODUCTION

Distribution networks (DNs) are experiencing a massive increase of distributed energy resources (DERs), which introduce bidirectional power flows and push the distribution equipment towards its limits. Many of the DERs, along with increasing numbers of loads, are interfaced to the DN by power converters. Conventional approaches require an independent conversion stage for every device, which degrades system efficiency, cost, and space availability.

Multiport power converters (MPCs) are an alternative conversion approach, which integrate three or more energy ports into a single device. MPCs can share components, which may improve the efficiency and cost [1]. Alternatively, an MPC might be configured as a collocated group of cascaded converters. Both configurations use a central controller that has low communications constraints and manages the power flows between ports [2].

The benefit that MPCs can provide to the DN can be considered in terms of system resilience features. Their highly controllable ports aggregate and manage power flows to mitigate network constraints while maintaining the protection of network areas. MPCs can encourage the deployment of energy storage systems (ESSs) and the central controller can optimise ESS utilisation, which has been shown to be a key feature of small system resilience [3]. Additionally, their low dependence on communications can reduce the risk of cyberattack and they may offer new measurement-dense locations to improve the visibility of the DN.

The resilience provided to DN by MPCs could be enhanced by equipping the converter with grid-forming control (GFM). GFM controllers aim to operate a converter as a voltage-source, different to grid-followers (GFLs) that aim to operate a converter as a current-source [4]. The voltage-source operation is robust in systems that have weak voltage stiffness, for example: at the end of long feeders, on systems that already have a large penetration of GFLs, or in islanded systems. Voltage-source behaviour can also improve the stability margins of neighbouring GFL devices [5]. Therefore, a GFM MPC could utilise its large aggregated energy resource to improve the reliability of converter supply in weak or islanded grids.

Although the features of a GFM MPC offer significant benefits to improve DN resilience, combining the technologies can be challenging. This paper introduces a GFM MPC for an enhanced soft open point (ESOP) application, discusses its hard- and software features that can enhance DN resilience, and the hurdles that limit its deployment.

APPLICATION SPECIFICATIONS

A soft-open point (SOP) is a converter-based solution that is used to mitigate network constraints in overloaded DN by connecting radial feeders and sharing available power between them. The SOP must also limit fault propagation across the DN [2]. The SOP's flexibility can be enhanced by collocating an ESS to support peak shaving or grid support. This configuration is often described as an enhanced soft open point (ESOP). An example ESOP case in the Spanish DSO Anell's DN will be used to analyse the proposed GFM MPC topology throughout the remainder of this study. The case includes: two 20 kV 400 kVA AC DN feeder ports with a collocated 400 V 100 kW ESS port. The choice of topology for the ESOP application is critical for resilience as it will influence the reliability of components, the severity of component failure, the availability of energy, and the controllability of the DN power flows. The topology will also influence the dependence on communications and the capability to support advanced control functionality. The choice of high-level control strategy is then critical to determine which conditions the converter can operate in, which functionality it can offer to maintain load service, and the speed that this can be provided.

MULTI-PORT POWER CONVERTER TOPOLOGY

Compared to conventional two-port SOP topologies, MPCs have the potential to offer: the integration of ESSs (to improve peak shaving, low-carbon energy utilisation, and grid support), lower dependence on communications for centralised control, and an improved number of conversion stages or components (which can reduce the probability of component failure but might increase the hazard associated with failure). The choice of topology determines exactly which features the MPC possesses.

High efficiency DC non-isolated topologies have been developed to integrate three DC ports with a very low number of components [6]. However, they can struggle to support the required power flows for the three highly controllable bidirectional ports for the ESOP application

Table 1 Resilient features relating to different components of the multipower power converter's topology.

Feature	FB SM	MMC	ISOP DAB
Power controllability	n/a	Bidirectional flow [7]	Bidirectional flow [8]
Voltage modulation ability	3 voltage levels [7]	Positive and negative voltages (with FB SM), enabling independent AC and DC voltage modulation [7]	Transformer operation enforces the modulation of only positive voltages, which couples the modulation of AC and DC voltages [8]
Reliability/failure rate	Degraded by high number of switches [9]	Improved by low number of SMs (due to low intermediate DC voltage) [9]	Improved by low number of series components (due to low intermediate DC voltage) [10]
Redundant power paths	Ability to bypass switches or capacitor	Ability to bypass SMs and the potential to add redundant SMs, which has been shown to reduce mean time between failure [9]	Failure of input series switches will increase the voltage stress on remaining healthy switches and could force total shutdown. However, the output parallel configuration offers redundant paths for de-rated operation in case of failure on this side
Port fault tolerance	n/a	Negative arm voltage supports mitigation of AC/DC short circuit fault current and continued operation [7]	Isolation stage limits the propagation of fault current from either side, however, the coupled AC and DC sides require shutdown (zero voltage) to de-energise and depend on current transformer (or similar) to identify fault within single switching period [8]
Communications requirement	Communications risk is minimised by the collocation of the converter stages [2]		

and they're not highly scalable, meaning they become expensive or infeasible for medium voltage applications. More conventional non-isolated cascaded AC/DC topologies can offer better scalability for medium voltages, higher operational flexibility, and higher technological maturity [7]. These topologies can be associated with a large number of components and are normally interfaced with line-frequency transformers, which degrade the topology's cost, size, and efficiency.

Isolated topologies achieve electrical separation of each port, which is normally achieved using a central transformer composed of multiple windings and/or cores [11]. These topologies generally offer high fault tolerance, voltage scalability, and operational flexibility but compromise cost, size, and complexity (considering the potential port interactions). Partially isolated topologies may offer a balance of the features of non- and fully-isolated topologies.

The following subsection will introduce the MPC topology that is being pursued for the ESOP application and justify the choice in terms of a range of techno-economic features often considered during the design of an MPC. The impact that these features have on the resilience of the MPC or the wider DN are discussed (and overviewed in Table 1).

Topology choice

A partially isolated topology, pictured in Figure 1, is chosen due to the balance of functionality, complexity, and cost. The topology is composed of two back-to-back

Figure 1 Partially isolated multiport power converter topology. modular multilevel converters (MMCs), both with full-

bridge (FB) submodules (SMs), that act as the SOP connection between the two medium voltage (MV) AC DN feeders. The intermediate DC link between the MMCs interfaces to the DC ESS via an input-series output-parallel dual-active bridge (ISOP DAB) converter configuration. The FB MMC offers the ability to operate in AC boost mode, stepping a lower intermediate DC voltage up to the higher AC voltage levels. This has been shown to offer a good balance of SM and therefore semiconductor numbers and AC power quality [10]. Additionally, the FB MMC is capable of negative AC and DC voltage modulation, which enables the converter to better handle electrical faults [7]. Although this topology possesses a large number of components (increasing the probability of failure) the redundant power paths improve the reliability [9]. An isolated stage is desirable to achieve the voltage gain between the low voltage ESS and the intermediate DC voltage (V_{DC}) and to provide a barrier to limit fault propagation. The ISOP DAB configuration is used as it allows the series configuration of switches on the higher voltage side. The number of series DC converter stages is reduced due to the lower intermediate DC voltage achieved by the FB MMC, which reduces the number of components and risk of failure.

GRID-FORMING CONTROL

Grid-forming control enables the MPC to further enhance resilience by supporting ESOP operation on weaker grids and improving the stability of neighbouring GFL converters. Additionally, GFMs provide transient injections to stabilise the network throughout disturbances and enable the establishment of islanded operation or black-start resynchronisation.

However, GFM control faces two significant issues for its implementation with MPCs on DNs. The first is the lower X/R ratio of the DN that degrades a conventional GFM's operation and the second is the integration of the GFM strategy into the highly coupled MPC device.

Impact of low X/R

MV DN X/R (between ~1 and 5 [12]) is lower than that of transmission networks (≥ 10), which P-f Q-V GFMs are designed for, but significantly higher than that of resistive microgrids (≤ 0.5), which P-V Q-f GFMs are designed for. The intermediate X/R level deviates from the conditions that each control approach is designed for and can therefore be expected to degrade their dynamics. Hereon the P-f Q-V strategy pictured in Figure 2 will be analysed to identify the impacts that the X/R has on its dynamics. A P-f Q-V strategy is analysed as the MPC will integrate with the MV DN, whose X/R is expected to be ≥ 1 and is operated according to P-f Q-V couplings.

The GFM controller is composed of outer loops (a first order P-f and second order Q-V droop controller), a current-limiting virtual impedance, and cascaded voltage and current controllers, which are described throughout [12]. This subsection will analyse the fundamental features

Figure 2 Grid-forming control strategy.

Figure 3 Impact of X/R on a converter's steady-state power transfer.

of a single GFM port (neglecting DC dynamics) connected to a simple Thevenin Equivalent representation of the power system before its integration into the MPC is considered.

The steady-state active power transfer of the GFM (and indeed any voltage source converter) can be described by (1), which is determined by the GFM's sending E and load's receiving voltage V magnitudes, the angle between them δ , and the coupling resistance R_t and reactance X_t between them.

$$P = \frac{EVR_t \cos(\delta) - E^2 R_t + EVX_t \sin(\delta)}{R_t^2 + X_t^2} \quad (1)$$

The feasible power transfer described by (1) is pictured as a function of δ for a range of X/R conditions in Figure 3. The figure depicts the reduction of feasible power transfer as X/R decreases through MV DN conditions, with particularly significant reductions for rectification (positive power).

A small-signal model of the GFM and simple power system is derived (according to the procedure described in [12]). A participation factor analysis across the range of X/R conditions finds most modes to maintain their state dependence apart from Modes 16,17 and Mode 18, which exhibit inverse variation in state dependence. Modes 16,17 (18) depend on voltage control in the low (high) X/R

Table 2 Resilient features of the grid-forming controller.

Feature	GFM controller
Device protection	Can struggle to effectively control current and retain synchronization throughout faulted conditions, which has knock-on effects for the MPC's energy management.
Feasible power transfer	All $P - \delta, Q - V$ controlled VSCs are equally degraded in low X/R. The reduction of transfer ability degrades transient stability margins and increases PQ coupling. As X/R decreases: GFM's outer loops are destabilised while its inner loops are stabilised.
Small-signal stability	GFLs are found to experience similar inner loop stabilisation [13]. As SCR decreases: GFMs are stabilised while GFLs are destabilised [13].
Time domain properties	As X/R decreases: GFM has slower PQ tracking but weaker NMPZ behaviour.
Impact on neighbouring devices	GFMs have the potential to stiffen weak grids to improve neighbouring GFL stability but also has the potential to fight with other voltages on strong grids [5]
Isolated operation	GFM is necessary for islanded and black start re-energisation.

Figure 4 Impact of X/R on grid-former's small-signal stability.

Figure 5 Impact of X/R on grid-former's time-domain properties.

conditions before transitioning to depend on angle generation as X/R increases (decreases).

Figure 4 exhibits a mixture of stabilising and destabilising pole movements (crosses) as X/R is increased. Current dependent modes 5,6 (subplot a) and 14 (subplot d) and voltage filter dependent modes 11,12 (subplot b) move towards the right-half plane (RHP). In contrast, the modes that swap dependence (16,17, subplot c, and 18, subplot e) move away from the RHP. Figure 4 a) also depicts the

 Figure 6 Response of the MPC following a three-phase fault (at $t = 0.1$ s and cleared after 250 ms) on DN feeder 1.

movement of two of the system's zeroes (circles) to the right, one of which crosses into the RHP at $X/R = 0.32$. Figure 5 depicts the time-domain active and reactive power responses of the GFM to a 0.1 PU inverting power reference step from a constant initial operating point. Both active and reactive power responses speed up as X/R increases, which agrees with the movement of the angle generation and voltage control dependent modes away from the RHP. The reactive power response exhibits worsening non-minimum-phase-zero behaviour, which agrees with the movement of the zero into the RHP. These results partially agree with [13], but extend the analysis to show that there is a mixture of destabilising and stabilising impacts as X/R varies.

Integration into the multiport power converter

Two GFM strategies, identical to that detailed in Figure 2, are implemented to control the AC ports of a simplified representation of the MPC pictured in Figure 1. The ESS manages the DC voltage.

Figure 6 depicts the voltage and current of GFM port 1

following a three-phase fault (at $t=0.1$ s) on the feeder it connects to. The MPC transmits 0.1 PU active power from GFM port 2 to GFM port 1 before the fault and is capable of maintaining operation throughout the disturbance. The virtual impedance limits the current to the maximum allowable magnitude (I_{max}) although some overshoot is experienced throughout the transient. GFM port 2's current and AC voltage (not pictured) remain unaffected throughout the fault due to the ESS's management of V_{DC} .

CONCLUSIONS

A partially isolated multiport power converter (MPC) has been introduced for a medium voltage enhanced soft open point application. The topology has low dependence on communications and minimises the number of components. The full-bridge submodules provide fault tolerance and redundancy, however, the series input DC stage may degrade the converter's reliability. Additional analysis will consider the alternate use of a modular multi-level DC converter for improved reliability before the topology is optimised.

Grid-forming control is suggested to be used to improve the converter's reliability in weak and islanded grids. However, the distribution network's X/R ratio is shown to have several impacts on the controller's operation. A simplified model of the MPC can operate with two GFM ports on separate feeders throughout a fault while an energy storage system manages the DC voltage. Future work should verify the MPC's conversion stages and modulation in more detail. Following this verification, the impact of port loss on the MPC should be explored as well as the robustness of its fault ride through.

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